

Real-Time Driver Drowsiness Detection Using CNN Approach and Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR) Analysis

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Abstract

This paper focuses on developing a software application for drivers, which helps in detecting signs such as yawning and eye closure by utilizing real-time video analysis. This software is made using a convolutional neural network (CNN) to analyze the facial images of yawning. It also computes the Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR) to detect prolonged eye closure. If drowsiness is detected, the system triggers an alarm sound to alert the driver. On continuous signs of drowsiness, it also sends an email to the emergency contact. This aims to prevent accidents caused by driver fatigue. This system is cost-effective, robust, and can be deployed easily in a variety of vehicles.

Keywords: Drowsiness, CNN, Eye Aspect Ratio, Alarm, OpenCV.

I. INTRODUCTION

Every day, we encounter a large number of accidents. The main reason for most accidents is "drowsiness of drivers." These road accidents cause severe injuries, fatalities, and property damage. When a driver is sleepy, they lose the ability to react faster, lack awareness of the situation, and lose decision-making abilities. These situations raised the necessity to develop a drowsiness detection system that continuously monitors the driver's alertness and takes preventive measures when fatigue is detected. The project aims to provide a prevention measure for accidents that take place due to driver fatigue. This system utilizes computer vision and machine learning to monitor the eye movement of drivers and detect yawning patterns.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Driver drowsiness detection is extensively studied because of its potential in decreasing fatigue-related road accidents. Numerous approaches such as physiological signals, facial features, sensor-based and hybrid systems have been looked into. Methods based on EEG [2] provide accurate detection based on brain activity, but they have challenges when it comes to practicability and user comfort. Computer vision methods, like PERCLOS [4], are efficient in tracking the closure of eyes and head movements but are susceptible to lighting and physical changes. Sensor-based methods [3] track vehicle conduct, such as steering trends and lane swerving, giving non-intrusive alerts, though with reduced accuracy. Hybrid systems [1] using combinations of methods give better precision but are more complex and costly. Realistic applications in car systems, like those employing Raspberry Pi for real-time monitoring [5], have been found to be promising under different conditions.

Although much progress has been made, future work needs to emphasize improving hybrid techniques, sensor technologies, and user acceptance to design more efficient and user-friendly drowsiness detection systems.

III. DRIVER'S DROWSINESS DETECTION

A. Importance

The main factors that lead to road accidents, especially for long-haul drivers and individuals driving for a long time without taking rest, are fatigue and drowsiness. Studies say that the drowsiness of drivers is the main reason for a large number of traffic accidents, which lead to injuries and fatalities. When drivers are drowsy, they can't react quickly to situations and lose the ability to make the right decisions. A continuous monitoring is required to make sure the driver's safety.

B. Challenges

Despite their benefits, these systems have limitations, including false alarms, environmental influences, and individual variances that might reduce accuracy. Powerful computers are required for real-time processing, and physiological sensors can be intrusive. High implementation costs and privacy concerns are additional barriers to widespread use.

IV. ROLE OF CNN

A. Overview

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are deep learning models that are particularly tailored for image and video analysis. They are best suited for extracting useful features from images, which is why they are well-suited for driver drowsiness detection, where there is a need for real-time facial analysis. In this paper, CNN is employed to analyze facial images or video frames of the driver, detect drowsiness-related features, and classify the state of the driver as alert or drowsy.

B. CNN in Driver's Drowsiness Detection

With Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for Detecting Yawning

There are several layers in the CNN architecture used in

this case:

Feature extraction is done using convolutional layers.

- Max pooling layers for down sampling.
- For the fully connected layers, apply the flattening layer to convert data to a one-dimensional form.
- For differentiation, between yawning and non-yawning frames, apply dense layers.
- The output layer employs the SoftMax Activation Function to predict data into two classes: yawn and no-yawn.
- Calculating the Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR)

C. Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR)

EAR is computed as:

- $EAR = \frac{\text{distance between two vertical eye landmarks}}{\text{distance between two horizontal eye landmarks}}$
- If EAR is below a threshold for an extended period, the system marks it as a drowsiness indicator.
- Evaluation Metrics:

The system calculates Precision, Recall, and F1 Score using the count of True Positives, False Positives, True Negatives, and False Negatives, enabling performance measurement and tuning.

D. ARCHITECTURE

Fig (1): SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The driver drowsiness detection system takes a photo of the driver's face using a camera and processes it through Dlib Facial Landmark Detection to recognize significant features, specifically eye positions. A CNN-based model scans the image for drowsiness signs, such as yawning detection and Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR) calculation to check if the eyes are closed. Upon detecting drowsiness, the system alarms the driver. For scenarios of frequent drowsiness, an email alert is sent to an emergency contact for security purposes. If no drowsiness is sensed, the system goes on monitoring the driver in real time. Integrating CNN and facial landmark detection, this system effectively reduces the risk of accidents by issuing timely warnings depending on analysis of eye closure and yawning.

IMPLEMENTATION

1.Data Collection and Preparation:

Collected a dataset with images of yawning and non-yawning faces. The data was augmented through image transformations such as flipping and zooming in order to enhance the model's robustness.

2.Training the CNN Model:

The CNN was trained from a labeled data set, and the images were separated into "yawn" and "no-yawn" classes. The ImageDataGenerator was applied to the preprocessing and augmentation, and the model was trained for many epochs with a categorical cross-entropy loss and Adam optimizer.

3.EAR Calculation for Blink Detection:

Facial landmarks around the eyes were detected, and EAR was calculated. A threshold was used to quantify eye closure over time, which, if sustained, indicated drowsiness.

4.Alert System Integration:

Implemented an integrated real-time alarm system that produces a sound and sends an email to the emergency contact through the smtplib library.

The integration enables timely notification to be forwarded to the driver and emergency contacts.

5. Testing and Evaluation: Accuracy testing was carried out by using the model in comparison to independent yawning and non-yawning face sets along with eye closure sequences. For estimating dependability in detection of drowsiness, measures of confusion matrix were recorded.

V. RESULT

This system works well in good lighting, reacting quickly to signs of tiredness.

Sample output

Fig (2) Drowsiness Alert

Fig (3) Alert Notification Sent

This evaluation metric summary shows the model's performance in detecting drowsiness. The accuracy (95.96%) shows that the model has a very low false positive rate, i.e., most of the detected drowsy cases are correct. The recall (89.62%) represents the model's ability to identify correctly drowsy cases, although some remain undetected (false negatives). The F1-score (92.68%) integrates precision and recall, confirming robust overall performance. The confusion matrix tallies (TP: 95, TN: 105, FP: 4, FN: 11) suggest that the model is very reliable with minimal misclassifications

Fig (4): Evaluation Metric

This below graph illustrates the training and validation loss (left) and accuracy (right) of the driver's drowsiness detection model with the Adam optimizer. The loss reduces gradually over epochs, reflecting good learning, while the accuracy improves, reflecting better performance. The validation curves track the training curves closely, reflecting little overfitting. The final accuracy is approximately 90%, reflecting good model performance. There are some variations in validation loss and accuracy that indicate minor instability but have little effect on overall trends.

Fig (5): Loss and Accuracy

The proposed CNN model consists of three convolutional layers with increasing filter sizes (32, 64, and 128) to learn hierarchical features. Max pooling is applied after every convolutional layer to decrease spatial dimensions without losing significant features. The flattened output goes through a 64-neuron fully connected layer before the final classification layer. This model in total contains 8.48 million trainable parameters, which ensures powerful learning ability. This architecture effectively combines feature extraction and computational efficiency for drowsiness detection.

```

Model: "sequential"
Layer (type)                Output Shape                Param #
-----
conv2d (Conv2D)              (None, 256, 256, 32)       320
max_pooling2d (MaxPooling2D) (None, 128, 128, 32)       0
conv2d_1 (Conv2D)            (None, 128, 128, 64)       18496
max_pooling2d_1 (MaxPooling2D) (None, 64, 64, 64)         0
conv2d_2 (Conv2D)            (None, 64, 64, 128)        73856
max_pooling2d_2 (MaxPooling2D) (None, 32, 32, 128)        0
flatten (Flatten)            (None, 131072)             0
dense (Dense)                 (None, 64)                  8388672
dense_1 (Dense)              (None, 2)                   130
-----
Total params: 8,481,474
Trainable params: 8,481,474
Non-trainable params: 0
    
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Fig (6): Keras Sequential model

CONCLUSION

This system is a helpful tool for checking if a driver stays alert and avoiding accidents from tiredness. It gives real-time warnings, which help drivers remain awake and focused on driving. While it functions well in normal light conditions, it could become even better with improvements. These could include newer ways to detect drowsiness, adding night vision, and connecting it with the car's systems. With such upgrades, the system could offer more reliable performance in various driving conditions, ensuring roads are safer for everyone.

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